

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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PU - Public, fully open

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Data Management Plan

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**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

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1 Data management plan

1.1 Data summary

Questions	Answers
<p>1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use them for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.</p>	<p>This project re-used the following publicly available dataset:</p> <p>Dataset for the method validation of halogenated VOCs with TD-GC-MS/FID – the dataset was re-used for the method validation of halogenated VOCs with TD-GC-MS/FID in WP2 to see if the use of the protocol improves measurement uncertainty.</p> <p>No existing data has been considered for re-use and then discarded.</p>
<p>2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?</p>	<p>Experimental data was obtained and collected by the participants in WP1, WP2 and WP3. Calibration, measurement and validation data resulted from the preparation and validation of gas standards, from the validation of the protocol, and from the performance evaluation of industrial analysers</p> <p>Data was generated or re-used in the following formats: For graphics: jpeg (pdf, png, pptx, tif, ai only possible) For tables: odsu, opj, xlsx For texts: docx, pdf, txt, csv For numerical data: csv</p>
<p>3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p>	<p><i>Purpose of the data generation or re-use</i> Data were generated from several sources: measurements, calibrations, comparisons and validations. They will be used in meeting the project's objectives and in conference and peer-reviewed publications.</p> <p><i>Data generated in relation to the objectives of the project</i> Data were generated by the consortium in order to meet objectives 1, 2 and 3: preparation and the validation of reference gas standards, validation of the protocol, performance evaluation of commercial analysers</p> <p>The project has generated 27 datasets which have been grouped by topic as specified in the Annex (see below). The reasons for their collection/generation are specified below:</p> <p>Group A</p> <p>The preparation and validation data for ammonia, hydrogen chloride, sulphur compounds, terpenes gas transfers were collected to provide input to new preparations of gas transfers standards</p> <p>Group B</p> <p>The laboratory-based method validation data were collected to provide input to new analytical methods for total silicon, siloxanes, ammonia, halogenated volatile compounds, terpenes, hydrogen, carbon monoxide, oxygen and nitrogen</p> <p>Group C</p> <p>The field-based validation data were collected to provide input to new evaluation of industrial analysers and reference instrumentation</p> <p>Group A datasets contribute to meeting objective 1 Group B datasets contribute to meeting objective 2</p>

	<p>Group C datasets contribute to meeting objective 3</p> <p><i>Data re-used in relation to the objectives of the project</i> Data will be re-used in relation to objectives 1, 2 and 3: preparation and the validation of reference gas standards, validation of the protocol, performance evaluation of commercial analysers.</p> <p>The project re-used 1 dataset from outside of the project for the purposes specified in question 1 above. Their relation to the objectives of the project is specified below:</p> <p>Dataset for the method validation of halogenated VOCs with TD-GC-MS/FID – contributed to objective 2</p>
4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	The overall size of the data/research outputs was less than 1 GB
5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	<p><i>Data generated in the project</i> The generated data originated from several sources, which included: measurement, calibration, comparison and validation data</p> <p>The project generated 27 datasets. The provenance of the data generated is specified below: GROUPS A,B,C Datasets The provenance and context of the data were thoroughly documented to meet relevant standards using the Provenance and Context Content Standard (PCCS) Matrix. The data are accompanied by information on how they were captured, processed, analysed, and validated. Other relevant information was also provided.</p> <p><i>Re-used data</i> The existing data will originate from several sources, which include: participant's pre-existing data, data from the scientific literature</p> <p>The project re-used 1 dataset which originated from the following external sources (from outside of this project):</p> <p>Dataset for the method validation of halogenated VOCs with TD-GC-MS/FID. This dataset was from EMPIR 16ENG05. The data were accompanied by provenance information.</p>
6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?	<p>The data will be suitable for use by other research groups working on the following topics: biomethane and other energy gases. The data will also be useful for standardization committees including ISO/TC158/WG3, ISO/TC158/WG4, ISO/TC193/SC1/WG25 and CEN/TC408</p> <p>The data might be useful to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders from industry: biomethane producers, instrument providers... • NMIs/DIs working in the energy gases field: ... • Other scientists working in the field:...

1.2 Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) Data

1.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Questions	Answers
7 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?	Yes. Published data has a DOI obtained from an open access repository.

8 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.	Published data has a DOI obtained from an open access repository. The project ensured that these submissions contain sufficient meta data to be reused without restrictions. The metadata is open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provided information on the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); the European Partnership on Metrology funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers, the authors involved. Where applicable, the metadata included persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.
9 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?	Yes. Search keywords were added in the metadata for data uploaded to repositories. These were biomethane, validation, protocol, gas analysers, gas transfer standards
10 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Yes. The search keywords were selected by the consortium for each dataset based on their topic area. Zenodo complies with FAIR principles (https://about.zenodo.org/principles/). The metadata are indexed in a searchable resource. Metadata are licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata are exported via Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) and can be harvested.

1.2.2 Making data accessible

Questions	Answers
Repository:	
11 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	The data were made accessible by deposition in an open access repository. The project's 27 datasets and associated metadata, documentation and code were deposited in Zenodo (https://zenodo.org).
12 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	No, the data was uploaded via a standard procedure and require no special arrangements
13 Does the repository ensure that the data are assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes, Zenodo assigned an identifier (DOI) to each of the project's deposited datasets. The repository resolves the identifier to a digital object.
Data:	
14 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is	All of the data that are needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications/research outputs was made openly available.

Questions	Answers
also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	
15 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.	<p>The data used in scientific publications, posters and oral communications were/will be made available for re-use.</p> <p>The project has deposited their datasets in Zenodo (see above)</p>
16 Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?	Yes, Zenodo provides well described conditions for free and standardised access (see http://about.zenodo.org/policies/).
17 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	No restrictions on the use of the published data are envisaged.
18 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	Users are required to register to use the repository.
19 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	This consortium did not establish a Data Access Committee, because the project produced no sensitive data. All results are publicly available without restrictions.
Metadata:	
20 Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	Yes, metadata was made openly available and licensed using an appropriate open-access license CC0. Metadata will include the information necessary to (re)use the data.
21 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data are no longer available?	<p>The data will remain available and findable for the lifetime of the Zenodo repository, which is expected to be a minimum of 20 years.</p> <p>If data are withdrawn from Zenodo, the DOI and the URL of the original object are retained. In case of closure of the Zenodo repository, best efforts will be made by Zenodo to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.</p>
22 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data and will this be included? Will it be possible to include the	<p>Data can be read:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. By using openly available formats (ODT, PDF, MS Office, JPEG). 2. By sharing software to read the data. 3. By using specialised software: Matlab and Mathematica, Origin. Standard publicly available software was used

Questions	Answers
relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	<p>The project's datasets which have been deposited in Zenodo i) are accessible using the following software tools, ii) require the following documentation about the software, and iii) require the following software</p> <p>GROUPS A,B,C Datasets</p> <p>i) MS office. ii) No specialist software is required. iii) No source codes required</p>

1.2.3 Making data interoperable

Questions	Answers
23 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?	<p>The datasets are interoperable as Zenodo's basic metadata requirement is compliant with the DataCite's Metadata schema and OpenAIRE</p> <p>Standard vocabularies were used to ensure inter-disciplinary interoperability and re-use (sources: ISO, IEC or IUPAC for example ISO/IEC Guide 99:2007 – international vocabulary of metrology and the compendium of chemical terminology (IUPAC))</p>
24 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow their re-use, refinement or extension?	The compatibility of our project-specific ontologies and vocabularies was guaranteed through appropriate mappings (glossary, alignment tables, etc.) to more commonly used ontologies. In this unlikely case, our own ontologies or vocabularies will be created and published
25 Will your data include qualified references ¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	No, the project's datasets do not include any references to other data

1.2.4 Increase data re-use

Questions	Answers
26 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable	A short README file (e.g. Markdown) was provided together with the data, in order to enable data analysis and to facilitate data re-use.

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Questions	Answers
definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?	
27 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	<p>The data were licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) version 4.0. Users will be required to acknowledge the consortium and the source of the data in any resulting publications. The project's datasets have been grouped by topic. The project's datasets which have been deposited in Zenodo include the following licenses (where necessary):</p> <p>1. GROUPS A,B,C Datasets Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY).</p>
28 Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	<p>The data published in open-access journals are usable by third parties as the datasets have been deposited in Zenodo. The data that do not relate to peer-reviewed publications were not made available.</p>
29 Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	<p>Yes, the provenance and context of the data was thoroughly documented to meet relevant standards using the Provenance and Context Content Standard (PCCS) Matrix. Data were accompanied by information on how they were captured, processed, analysed, and validated. Other information was also provided</p>
30 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	<p>Data quality was assured through repeated and comparison measurements, adherence to standards for data recording, the use of controlled vocabularies and standard terminology, through the metrological characterisation of the measurement set-ups and through the validation of the data collected. Other quality assurance processes included the provision of test results along with the data and the peer-review of publications based on the data</p>
31 Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	<p><u>Allocation of resources</u> The costs for making the (data and) other research outputs FAIR was 1 000 € (personnel costs) (see question 34). The costs for making other research outputs FAIR are included in the project's budget and will be claimed if compliant with the Grant Agreement's conditions. Long term preservation was ensured by depositing the other research outputs in repositories. The Data Access Committee decided on a case-by-case basis which other research outputs were deposited and for how long.</p> <p><u>Security of other research outputs</u> All participants are either accredited to, or work in compliance with, the ISO 17025 standard on the "General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories". The participants stored other research outputs on their organisations' networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Other research outputs were also stored in the project's SharePoint environment, with a password-protected login. Deposition in public repositories provides additional security as they have multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis. This project did not generate sensitive other research outputs. The other research outputs are safely stored in open access repositories.</p> <p><u>Ethical aspects</u> There were issues that could impact on the sharing of other research outputs.</p>

Questions	Answers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information relating to other research outputs acquired from third parties, e.g. manufacturers, was not shared without their explicit consent. Information relating to other research outputs collected by the consortium at commercial sites was not shared without the site owner's explicit consent. Ethical issues were addressed as the project prepared an ethics report. <p>The project did not share other research outputs with identifiable personal information. Sensitive information relating to the other research outputs was collected, separated as soon as possible and kept secure.</p> <p>Please also see the information provided in section 1.3 below.</p>

1.3 Other research outputs

Questions	Answers
32 In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	Research outputs included new: calibration methods, protocols and materials. The main objective of the project was to develop a versatile protocol for the verification, validation and performance evaluation of the analytical instruments. The project shared its protocol with ISO/TC193/SC1/WG25 on for feedback from scientists outside of the consortium. The protocol has then been used to draft a new work item proposal (and later on an ISO standard)
33 Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.	As far as possible, the FAIR data approaches specified in questions 7-30 above were applied to the management of this project's other research outputs. This commitment was met by placing the protocol in a trusted repository in line with the requirements of the project's consortium agreement (see the answer to question 32 for further details).

1.4 Allocation of resources

Questions	Answers
34 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?	The costs for making the data and other research outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) were 1 000 € (personnel costs). These costs were kept to a minimum by using a free repository (Zenodo) and by making only relevant data and other outputs FAIR.
35 How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part	The costs for making the data FAIR were included in the project's budget and will be claimed as they were compliant with the Grant Agreement's conditions.

of the European partnership on metrology grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).	
36 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?	The project manager for the lead organization had overall responsibility for data management. The coordinator led this committee and was responsible for coordinating updates to the data management plan. The committee were responsible for organising data backup and storage, data archiving and for depositing the data within the repositories (Zenodo).
37 How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?	<p>Long term preservation was ensured by depositing the data within a repository (Zenodo), where they are guaranteed to be stored for at least 10 years. No costs were associated with the long-term preservation of the data in these repositories.</p> <p>The data will increase in value over time because of its fundamental impact in a wide range of applications. It will enable the methods validated in the project to be taken up by the measurement supply chain and by standards bodies including ISO/TC193/SC1/WG25 Biomethane Working Group and CEN TC408 WG1. These standards bodies will need access to the data to justify the robustness of future standards. The data will also be of value as it underpins the results of published datasets</p>

1.5 Data security

Questions	Answers
38 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	<p><u>Data recovery and secure storage</u> All participants are either accredited to, or work in compliance with, the ISO 17025 standard on the “General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories”. The participants stored data on their organisations’ networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Data were also stored in the project’s SharePoint environment, with password protected login. Deposition in the Zenodo public repository provided additional security as it has multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis.</p> <p><u>Transfer of sensitive data</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This project did not generate sensitive data.
39 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Yes, the data are/will be safely stored in the Zenodo open access repository

1.6 Ethics

Questions	Answers
40 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include	<p>There were issues that could impact on data sharing: Data collected by the consortium at commercial sites was not shared without the site owner’s explicit consent. Data may be anonymised or not disclosed after these discussions. The data from the survey was made anonymous to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).</p>

Questions	Answers
references to ethics report(s) and the ethics section in the Annex 1.	
41 Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation was included in the market and customer surveys. The project did not share data with identifiable personal information. Sensitive data were collected, separated as soon as possible and kept secure

1.7 Other issues

Questions	Answers
42 Do you, or will you, make use of other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?	Data management was compliant with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The research data policy of the European Partnership on Metrology; • European laws about data security and the protection of privacy (e.g. GDPR); • Institutional guidelines; • Scientific community guidelines

Annex: overview of the datasets in this periodic data management plan

This project has generated 27 datasets. These have been grouped by topic / method / format / type as described below. The answers to the questions in this periodic DMP relate to the groups defined below.

GROUP A (<https://zenodo.org/records/17542711>)

1. Dataset on amount fractions for siloxanes standard measurement
2. Dataset on amount fractions for siloxanes standard measurement
3. Dataset on amount fractions for sulphur standard measurement
4. Dataset on amount fractions for ammonia standard measurement
5. Dataset on amount fractions for hydrogen standard measurement
6. Dataset on amount fractions for nitrogen standard measurement
7. Dataset on amount fractions for oxygen standard measurement
8. Dataset on amount fractions for bulk matrix standard measurement
9. Dataset on amount fractions for bulk matrix standard measurement
10. Dataset on amount fractions for carbon monoxide standard measurement

GROUP B (<https://zenodo.org/records/17542820>)

11. Dataset for method validation for total silicon with AES
12. Dataset for method validation for siloxanes with TD-GC-MS/FID
13. Dataset for method validation for siloxanes with GC-IMS
14. Dataset for method validation for halogenated VOC with TD-GC-MS/FID
15. Dataset for method validation for sulphur compounds with GC-SCD
16. Dataset for method validation for sulphur compounds with GC-SCD-FID
17. Dataset for method validation for terpenes with TD-GC-MS/FID

18. Dataset for method validation for hydrogen with GC-TCD
 19. Dataset for method validation for carbon monoxide with GC-TCD
 20. Dataset for method validation for nitrogen with GC-TCD
 21. Dataset for method validation for CO O2 H2 N2 with GC-TCD
 22. Dataset for method validation for bulk gases with GC-TCD

GROUP C (<https://zenodo.org/records/17542882>)

23. Dataset on amount fraction siloxanes– online measurement
 24. Dataset on amount fraction terpenes – online measurement
 25. Dataset on amount fraction ammonia – online measurement
 26. Dataset on amount fraction carbon monoxide –online measurement
 27. Dataset on amount fraction methane ethylene – online measurement

2 Open science: research data management

Statement	Put an X in the box to confirm	Or, list any exceptions to this
All participants have adhered to the requirements of the project's GA and CA with respect to open science: research data management (GA Article 17 and its Annex 5) for this reporting period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	